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Revisiting Human-Nature Boundary in Bao Ninh’s “A River’s Mystery”: A Perspective on Posthuman Ecology

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Abstract:

The objective of this research paper is to find how the short story of Bao Ninh exhibits a subtle human-nature bonding that the anthropocentric human civilization has long been ignoring and attempting to push to the periphery, devaluating it to the extent of dwindling nature’s existence along with its flora and fauna, and the rich biodiversity as the ‘other’. In this present anthropocentric world, Nature is regarded to retain some value only as long as it satisfies the human needs. An attempt has been made to explore how nature and the natural environment in the domain of human existence differ from the destructive and authoritative representation of nature in Bao Ninh’s “A River’s Mystery”. The Vietnamese writer, Bao Ninh represents in his work how nature appears in ferocious forms and victimizes human beings. Anthropocentrism is questioned in both the South Asian and Southeast Asian short stories. Theoretical concept of ecocriticism has been used in this study for examining the combined roles of human beings and the natural environment. This study uses a content analysis method and the study reveals that human beings affect nature differently and, also nature affects human beings differently, under varied circumstances and situations. The study also reveals that nature takes revenge and expresses its destructive authority over human

beings irrespective of class, gender or societal identity. This study concludes that the actions, reactions and responses of human beings to nature and vice-versa confirm the theoretical relevance of Posthumanism differently with respect to the short story of Bao Ninh.

Keywords: Posthumanism, rivers, environment, anthropocentrism, boundary.

The river, in Bao Ninh's "A River's Mystery" (1996) is a representative of nature. The river, here, is authoritative and destructive. The river, as a representative of nature, is arrogant, tyrannic and autocratic. The actions and effects of destruction brought about by the flooding river challenges the powers and actions of human beings. The river is represented with an anti-anthropocentric approach towards boasting human beings. Moreover, as an embodiment of nature, in this short story, the river acts quite differently in that it ravages the lives of the villagers indiscriminately, without any proper justification of their actions, reactions and their responses towards the elements of nature. The short story depicts the flooded river as a monster that sweeps and engulfs everything that it finds in its way, indiscriminately. Even the good ones are lashed by the cruel destiny that appears in the form of the flooded river. Reward and punishment are not evenly distributed in the short story "A River's Mystery". Though Harold Fromm has observed, "Western man does not generally live in fear of Nature, except when earthquakes or cancer strike, for he is mostly unaware of a connection with Nature that has been artfully concealed by modern technology" (Fromm 33), the environmental concern in the present day world has evinced that not only the Western man but the entire world is in fear of environmental disasters.

All the human beings are placed under the mercy of this nature's representative called the flooded river, from whom none can escape. The flooded river is anti-anthropocentric. The protagonist of the short story, his wife, his newborn baby boy, and the villagers - all are made

poor victims of the mighty river. The mystery of the river is ever retained and the suspense is maintained throughout the short story. The river thrives in mystery and remains mysterious so long as the text exists and is enlivened every time the readers read the text. The river remains shrouded in mystery even when the story ends.

The river is more powerful than human beings in that the mystery of the river remains unresolved generations after generations and the human beings, unable to solve their mystery, rather becomes mystery in itself and thus the mysterious events in the lives of the human beings only add to the list and heap up to the aggregate sad mysterious incidents of the villager's lives. The sad realization of the narrator, in the beginning of the short story, delineates the omnipresence of the mighty river:

“Rivers, like time, flow without stopping. Like time, they bear witness to many happenings. This is true especially at night when the river that winds through my village sparkles with thousands of mysterious luminous points. Among them lies the secret story of my life” (Ninh 107).

The river is always present in the minds of the villagers. The dark shadow of the river looms large and takes a toll in the lives of all the villagers. The horrific memories of the devastation and havoc caused by the flooded river levels down all the villagers in an equal plane and shakes off their boasting attitude of excelling over one another. Nature bears the power to equalize all human beings under equal footings. Nature blurs the boundary of human differentiation:

“The village was completely submerged in water. I had just managed to get my family up to our roof when a second tide swept in. In an instant, the thatched roof was spirited away into the dark night. Luckily, it got caught up in the branches of a banyan tree where it sat precariously suspended as the tide threatened to rip it to shreds. A crowd of villagers was also

clinging to the limbs of the big tree. Several hands reached down to pull us up" (Ninh 107-08).

Tides swept in one after another and crumbled the villagers on top of the banyan tree, which is again an embodiment of nature. The villagers, in the moment of crisis, were bound to seek shelter and protection that only nature could provide them. Nature becomes mightier than the human beings who think themselves to be superior because of their higher intellectual levels.

The river is an embodiment of nature in Bao Ninh's short story, "A River's Mystery" (1996) and takes revenge on human beings. The river, a representative of nature, explicates the magnitude of its power to take revenge and puts up resistance to the unprecedented ravishing of nature. The swelling and upsurging river, the wild storm and the frightful situation threatened the human beings who did not pay heed to the impending threats to the effects of overall global warming and climate change:

"The storm raged for several more hours. The river stopped rising, but its current remained strong. More people landed in our tree, which began to look like an overcrowded boat running aground. It was a very dangerous situation. With one hand holding the tree and the other clutching my wife tightly, I grew overcome by exhaustion. My wife seemed weaker and weaker; her body was drenched and cold, but she still tried to keep the baby from getting wet." (Ninh 108).

The unnamed first person narrator in the short story has not been given any name deliberately as he represents all the human beings taken together. The unnamed wife in the same way is a victim of the enraged nature and represents all the human beings taken together. The unnamed narrator, his wife and the villagers are representative of the global human beings who are directly or indirectly connected with the effects of climate change, global warming

and the exploitation of mother nature in a global perspective. The village in the story is a miniature of the entire globe that is suffering from disastrous effects of sudden floods, global warming, climate change effects and dangerous pollution effects. Rosi Braidotti in *More Posthuman Glossary* (2022) observed, “After centuries of intense activity at the behest of some humans in the Minority World, we seem to be witnessing the collapse of the climate and ecosystems that defined the stability of the Holocene epoch” (17).

Nature turns back and puts a reply to the villagers. Even a newborn baby is snatched from the mother. The mother is helpless in the face of odds and cannot save her child from the rage of the flooded river, which engulfs all that comes to its way:

“Towards dawn, I heard a sudden thud below the tree, followed by the cry of a woman choking on water.

‘Help us!’ she cried. ‘Help my baby and me! Oh, heavens!’” (Ninh 108).

The flooded river chokes the women on water. Nature pays back. The waves of the seas return all that it takes from the shore. It takes nothing except the life of a person drowned in it. Similarly, the flooded river takes the lives of people of the village. Human beings, from the global perspective, have been continually choking the pure and green environment by different ways of pollution - land, water, air, sound, and even light pollution. Now, nature chokes human beings and takes its revenge. The flood mocks the human beings and enters into a power struggle to restore its lost supremacy over human beings. Graham Huggan and Helen Tiffin observed, “mock-pastoral becomes, for the narrator, a simulacral reality filtered through borrowed visions from other writers’ fantasies; even though these visions are corrected by experience, they restore a secondary pastoralism which, disappearing by design, re-emerges by default” (114).

They are made to be observed as punny puppets in the hands of the enraged river, a representative of nature. The villagers are subdued by the mighty power of the flooded river. They are made to accept their defeat against the enormous forces of nature. The uninterrupted exploitation of nature by human beings is protested by the action of the flooded river, which sweeps and carries everything that comes on its way and brings about massive changes in the lives of the villagers even when the flood is already over. The ravages, loss of lives, deaths and destruction brought about by the flooded river has left a permanent imprint on the lives of the villagers. The unnamed narrator of the short story, "A River's Mystery" (1996) has lost his newborn baby and his dear wife in the flooded river. The memories of his wife and the newborn baby haunted the narrator throughout his life:

"A frozen hand thrust upward to catch mine but descended before I could grab it. Startled, I bent down, trying to seize it but not in time. The branch we were hanging on to began to shake violently. Frightened and nervous, my wife lost her grip. *Plop!* Our baby, whom I had still not been able to see, slipped out of the plastic bag where he lay in his mother's arm and into the dark torrents of the flood.

"Oh, God! My baby.." my wife screamed and plunged down into the water.

I dove after her. The water was cold, murky, deep, and flowing rapidly. Flailing around desperately, my hands came across the baby. I surfaced and handed it to the outstretched hands above. I then dived back into the current to search for my wife" (Ninh 108).

The mystery lies deep embedded in the baby, rescued by the narrator. It was not his own baby that his wife had slipped off her hands. This was a baby of another lady who along with her baby were victims of the flooded river. Unknowingly, the narrator saved another baby, thinking it to be his own and then dived into the river in search of his wife who was also drowned. The river snatched his baby and his wife from him forever and brought a drastic change in his life which he could never share with anyone else. The narrator was

rescued in a canoe full of flood victims. The river blurred the invisible boundary of rich, poor, educated, illiterate, man or woman. All were placed together in the same canoe, all were brought together and placed on equal footing. He was then handed over a baby and to his utter dismay he discovered it to be a baby girl instead of his own baby boy. He realized immediately the intricate mystery of the river and its actions on his life:

“The baby was a girl! I had saved the baby of the woman who had cried for help last night.

As for my son, he was with his mother in the cold, pitch dark abyss” (Ninh 109).

Entire life of the unnamed narrator was changed. Terry Gifford aptly observed, “the result of such a recognition is that the destructive-creative processes in the natural world provides images for understanding our inner process” (59). The mysterious outcome of the river shattered his life forever and left him beyond any reversible pathways. He was left with no other option but to bear in his heart, the horrible mystery of the river and the devastatingly sad mystery of his life till the last breath of his life:

“Since then much time and water have flowed by. I am now advanced in age, and my daughter has become the most beautiful girl in the village. Everybody calls her the child of the river because they all know that she fell into the stream and that I rescued her. But apart from the river and me, nobody, including my daughter, knows her real story” (Ninh 109- 10).

Bao Ninh has reversed the anthropocentric view of human beings in his short story, “A River’s Mystery” (1996). The river, in the short story appears as a challenging and authoritative figure to human beings. The facade of the human- centered world is broken and countered by the river which is both an embodiment of nature and a post-human authority. Natural disasters, frequent floods, global warming, and recent climate conditions are all the results of environmental degradation caused by human beings. The unnamed village and the unnamed villagers, as represented in the short story, looks like a miniature globe where

people are suffering due to recent unnatural climate conditions and are continually affected by environmental disasters. Kroker observed, "Foucault's understanding of posthuman power introduces us to contemporary global-ized society as one in which power increasingly announces itself in the language of the colonial subaltern, identifying with the language of the "culture of injury," the language of resentment and revenge-taking" (28).

"An altogether different and powerful source of inspiration for contemporary re-configurations of critical posthumanism is ecology and environmentalism" (Braidotti 48). Posthumanism advocates anti-anthropocentrism. Bao Ninh's river, an embodiment of nature and the Environment challenges anthropocentrism. The river is presented as an anti-anthropocentric entity of nature. The human centered worldview has been reversed in the ecocentric representation of the river in Bao Ninh's short story, "A River's Mystery" (1996). The human beings are made to bend down and stoop in front of nature:

"Every now and then I go up onto the levee and watch the river. My wife, my son, and the nameless woman seem to be looking up at me from the bottom of the river. Months and years have passed. The river and history have changed. But I have never recovered from my pain. Words are inadequate to describe it." (Ninh 110).

Herbrechter observed, "Post-anthropocentric posthumanities are still about humans and their cultures but only in so far as these are placed within a larger ecological picture, as can be seen, for example, in the proliferation and institutionalization of a variety of alternative "humanities," like the medical humanities, the environmental humanities, and the digital humanities"(19). There is a craving for a return to the past where pastoralism reigned. "It may be that one contemporary pastoral refuge lies within the discourse of ecology itself. At the root of pastoral is the idea of nature as a stable, enduring counterpoint to the disruptive energy and change of human societies" (Garrard 63). Human beings are bound to accept their

defeat to nature and acknowledge their triviality in comparison to the might of the environment and nature. Though the short story is a very sad and heart rendering one from the perspective of the irrecoverable mishap of the narrator who is a representative of the universal suffering man of all ages and deserves sympathy, still the nature's revenge on human beings on account of its mistreatment, mismanagement and endless exploitation does not escape the stance of the ecocritics and posthumanists. The river blurs the boundary of everything that comes and resists its path. The human-nature anthropocentric boundary, created by human beings, is thwarted and blurred. The river is made to assert its will to resist anthropocentrism and establish its own pagan religion where nature is supreme.

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